

TARGET

**SECOND NEWSLETTER
OUT NOW!**

Welcome to the second release of the TARGET Newsletter!

This biannual newsletter will take you on an insightful journey into the groundbreaking TARGET Project, keeping you informed and engaged with the latest developments, milestones, and insights from our project. Our goal is to introduce virtual twin-driven AI models for atrial fibrillation (AF) and its complications, such as AF-related stroke (AFRS), to improve patient outcomes and reduce healthcare costs.

In this edition, we present updates on our project, showcase recent events and conferences our researchers have attended, and highlight our latest publications. We extend our gratitude to our dedicated team members, whose hard work and passion make this project possible.

We hope you enjoy learning about the advancements of the TARGET team. Have a great read and stay tuned for more updates in the coming months!

**Enjoy the read!
The TARGET Team**

TARGET FIRST PAPER: AI-BASED DERIVATION OF ATRIAL FIBRILLATION PHENOTYPES IN GENERAL AND CRITICAL CARE POPULATIONS

The TARGET project's first paper, titled "**AI-based Derivation of Atrial Fibrillation Phenotypes in the General and Critical Care Populations**," introduces an innovative AI-based method using generative topographic mapping (GTM) to identify clinically relevant phenotypes of atrial fibrillation (AF) across diverse patient populations.

AF is the most common heart arrhythmia globally, associated with increased mortality and morbidity risks. Traditional clinical risk scores have limitations in predicting AF and its complications due to the complexity and heterogeneity of AF patients. This study, made possible through funding from **TARGET** and the **DECIPHER** project (LJMU QR-PSF), proposes an innovative AI-based methodology aimed at addressing these challenges by classifying patients into distinct, clinically meaningful phenotypes.

Using generative topographic mapping, a probabilistic machine learning method, the research successfully identified distinct clinical phenotypes of AF in both general and critical care populations, drawn from two large databases: **UK-Biobank** and **MIMIC-IV**. This approach can enhance the accuracy of patient stratification, making it possible to tailor prevention and treatment strategies more effectively for each phenotype.

Authors: Ryan A.A. Bellfield, Ivan Olier, Robyn Lotto, Ian Jones, Ellen A. Dawson, Guowei Li, Anil M. Tuladhar, Gregory Y.H. Lip, Sandra Ortega-Martorell

[READ THE FULL PAPER](#)

ADVANCING PERSONALISED CARE IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION AND STROKE: THE POTENTIAL IMPACT OF AI FROM PREVENTION TO REHABILITATION

A recent paper titled "Advancing personalised care in atrial fibrillation and stroke: The potential impact of AI from prevention to rehabilitation" published in the journal Trends in Cardiovascular Medicine, explores the transformative role of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) in managing atrial fibrillation (AF) and stroke. Highlighting the challenges of static risk prediction tools, the authors advocate for dynamic, AI-driven approaches to personalise risk assessment, treatment, and rehabilitation.

This paper underscores the critical need for continued research and the adoption of integrative strategies to optimise atrial fibrillation and stroke care, ultimately aiming to mitigate the substantial burden these conditions impose on patients and healthcare systems. This research need is what gave origin to projects such as TARGET.

Authors: Sandra Ortega-Martorell, Ivan Olier, Mattias Ohlsson, Gregory Y.H. Lip, TARGET Consortium

[READ THE FULL PAPER](#)

INTRODUCING THE CONSORTIUM TO SCIENTIFIC AUDIENCES

TARGET's programme of work and consortium was recently highlighted in two significant outlets. The first, featured in the European Heart Journal under the Cardio Pulse section, presents the aims and ambitions of the project to develop virtual twin technology for personalised stroke management in atrial fibrillation. The second is a Clinical Focus paper published on Thrombosis and Haemostasis, where we discuss the clinical challenges within the AF-related stroke disease pathway from prevention to rehabilitation, and provide an overview of the clinical observational studies.

[A European network to develop virtual twin technology for personalized stroke management in atrial fibrillation: the TARGET consortium.](#)

Ortega-Martorell S, Olier I, Lip GYH; TARGET consortium.

Eur Heart J. 2024 Nov 20:ehae673. doi: 10.1093/eurheartj/ehae673.

[TARGET: A Major European Project Aiming to Advance the Personalised Management of Atrial Fibrillation-Related Stroke via the Development of Health Virtual Twins Technology and Artificial Intelligence.](#)

Ortega-Martorell S, Olier I, Ohlsson M, Lip GYH; TARGET Consortium.

Thromb Haemost. 2024 Nov 7. doi: 10.1055/a-2438-5671.

TARGET CLINICAL STUDIES

WP 8, led by Liverpool University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, UK, consists of four clinical studies conducted at four EU centres. Two of the clinical studies focus on prediction and detection of very brief episodes of atrial fibrillation (AF) in acutely ill patients and those having suffered a stroke.

The NOTE-AF study, conducted in acutely ill patients and patients undergoing high-risk surgery, aims to identify subclinical and paroxysmal episodes of atrial fibrillation using a novel remote wireless patch-based monitoring device.

The TAILOR study addresses two primary topics: 1) the detection of (subclinical) atrial fibrillation in patients following an ischemic stroke or transient ischemic attack, and 2) the assessment of functional and cognitive outcomes in patients with AF-related stroke (AFRS), including sequential MR-imaging, extensive neuropsychiatric evaluation, and physical assessments. Patients will be followed over a period of one year.

The two rehabilitation studies, PEARL & FOSTER, investigate rehabilitation needs after stroke and usability of sensor measurements to determine recovery of patients. Recruitment for the clinical studies has started or is imminent for all 4 studies.

MEET THE EXPERT ADVISORY BOARD

On the 12th of November, we held our very first meeting with our **External Expert Advisory Board**, marking an exciting step forward in TARGET's journey. It was a pleasure to gather with such a talented and knowledgeable group, each bringing unique expertise and perspective to the table.

Together, we delved deep into TARGET's programme of work, discussed our ambitions, and shared ideas that will help drive impactful change. Having such passionate minds on board reinforces our commitment to delivering meaningful results, and we're energised by the path ahead.

Looking forward to more insightful conversations and collaborations as we work together to turn these ambitions into reality!

TARGET External Expert Advisory Board

 David Hernández Herrero Head of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Service Hospital Universitario La Paz, Spain			
 Alexis Paton Senior Lecturer in Social Epidemiology and the Sociology of Health Aston University, UK			

 TARGET has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe, under grant agreement GA n. 101136244

SPREADING THE WORD:

TARGET'S PARTICIPATION IN CONFERENCES, FAIRS, AND MULTIPLE EVENTS

TARGET has been presented at numerous prestigious events, showcasing its mission to advance artificial intelligence and digital twin technologies in healthcare. Highlights included its introduction to the cardiovascular community at the British Cardiovascular Society conference in April, emphasising the value of co-production, and a presentation at the NII Shonan Meeting in May, focusing on visual computing applications. TARGET's visibility extended to collaborations at TecnATox's PhD Day and outreach to Early Career Researchers at the RISES Summer School. It was featured prominently at international platforms like the Thessaloniki Fair, the EDITH-CSA Ecosystem Meeting, and DIGITALEUROPE's webinar on Virtual Human Twins.

Public engagement efforts, such as Soapbox Science Liverpool and World Heart Day events, connected TARGET with patients, families, and the general public. Further academic and healthcare outreach occurred through keynote lectures at the Cardiovascular Thrombosis Meeting in Spain, Blackpool Teaching Hospitals in the UK, and the Colombia Data Summit. These activities underscored TARGET's innovative mission to leveraging AI for improving cardiovascular and stroke patient care.

A summary of the activities during this period can be found below:

 6th April: TARGET was presented to the cardiovascular community at the British Cardiovascular Society conference by Dr Grahame Smith and Prof Deirdre Lane (TARGET's WP2 lead) with a communication on "How co-production adds value to a project: Our experiences from TARGET".

 15th May: TARGET was presented at the NII Shonan Meeting Seminar n.189 by Dr Renata Raidou (TUW), with a talk about 'Harnessing Visual Computing in Material Sciences through Insights from Biomedical Visualization'.

 5th July: TARGET was presented at the "PhD Day of TecnATox" in Catalonia, Spain (<https://www.tecnatox.cat/>) by Prof Domenech Puig and his team (WP7, URV). This visibility led to academic collaborations, sharing of ideas, and critical feedback that enhanced the quality and scope of the project research.

 7th July: Prof Sandra Ortega-Martorell (TARGET's PI), presented TARGET to the participants of the RISES Summer School: "Big Ideas, Big Data" celebrated in Liverpool, with a talk on 'Digital twins: what they are and how they help', showcasing TARGET as an example of development and use of these new technologies. This was a brilliant opportunity to connect with Early Career Researchers and spark ideas on how these new technologies can be applied to other research questions.

15th July: TARGET was presented at the Final EDITH-CSA Ecosystem Meeting in Amsterdam, as one of the projects leading the initiatives of health virtual twins development. Prof Ivan Olier (TARGET's methodological leader) and Dr Adam Knowles (TARGET's postdoc at LJMU) represented TARGET.

20th July: TARGET took part in the Soapbox Science Liverpool 2024. Our PI, Prof Ortega-Martorell, presented TARGET on the streets of Liverpool, where many people with AF, stroke survivors, and families of stroke patients, approached with interest in the research.

24th July: Heart Rhythm Updates Liverpool 2024, organised by Arrhythmia Alliance and chaired by Prof Gregory Lip (TARGET's clinical lead) and Prof Deirdre Lane. Prof Ortega-Martorell presented TARGET to healthcare providers and allied health professionals attending the event. "Keynote Lecture: Rise of The Machines: The Increasing Role of Artificial Intelligence in Atrial Fibrillation Management".

4th September: TARGET was presented by Dr Eva Giralt (co-lead of the TAILOR clinical study) and Dr Esther Duarte (lead of the PEARL clinical study) in the 'Nit the la Recerca, European Corner 2024' event celebrated in Barcelona, Spain (<https://lanitdelarecerca.cat/european-corner/>).

- **7th September:** TARGET was presented at the Thessaloniki Fair 2024 (<https://thessalonikifair.gr/en>), an annual trade and cultural exhibition held in Thessaloniki, Greece, showcasing innovations, commerce, and international collaborations. TARGET was presented by our partner CERTH, led by Dr Dimitrios Tsaopoulos.
- **19th September:** Prof Ivan Olier presented TARGET to the Cardiovascular Thrombosis Meeting - Spanish Society of Cardiology, with his keynote talk titled “Artificial Intelligence and its Applications in Cardiovascular Science”.
- **25th September:** TARGET was presented at the “Perspectives on Sustainability of the VHT from EU Member States and Key Partners” webinar organised by DIGITALEUROPE and EDITH. The event focused on the innovative Virtual Human Twin (VHT) initiative, which aims to revolutionise healthcare through digital human biology models to advance research, diagnostics, and treatments. A presentation by Dr Oliver Frings of Siemens Healthineers highlighted the TARGET project, showcasing it as an exemplary collaboration within the VHT ecosystem.
- **29th September:** TARGET, AFFIRMO and ARISTOTELES teamed up (clustering activity) to celebrate World Heart Day 2024 by raising awareness of heart health at Fylde Rugby Club. This activity was organised by Prof Deirdre Lane (UoL) and Dr Robyn Lotto (LJMU).
- **2nd October:** TARGET was on the front page of the Liverpool John Moores University website, with a news item highlighting the ‘Latest AI research to help stroke and cardiac patients’, featuring a short video of Prof Ortega-Martorell talking about the project.

16th October: TARGET was highlighted during the celebration of the 115th Anniversary of our partner Inkeendaal, represented by Prof Marc Degelaen (co-leading the FOSTER clinical study in TARGET), and Dr Elissa Embrechts.

16th October: Clustering activity between TARGET and PRESTIGE-AF. Fifteen researchers from TARGET (LJMU and UoL) took part in the PRESTIGE-AF Escape Room: 'Escape the Clinic!' and a Public Engagement workshop, discussing the importance of engaging with the public.

29th October: TARGET and PRESTIGE-AF teamed up (clustering activity) to celebrate World Stroke Day. The Liverpool Centre for Cardiovascular Sciences hosted a special health screening event aimed at raising awareness and promoting prevention! The team, led by Prof Lane (UoL), provided free screenings for high blood pressure and atrial fibrillation—two of the most common, yet often silent, risk factors for ischaemic stroke.

6th November: TARGET's PI was also the keynote speaker at an event in Blackpool, UK, to healthcare professionals at Blackpool Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, where she talked about 'The increasing role of AI and digital twins in healthcare: the TARGET project'.

14th November: TARGET was highlighted at the "Colombia Data Summit 2024", to an audience of over 300 data scientists, where Prof Olier and Prof Ortega-Martorell were keynote speakers.

18th to 24th November: To celebrate Global AF Aware Week 2024, TARGET joined the AF Association's effort to raise awareness about Atrial Fibrillation, with the theme, "Hearts Beating, Minds Meeting", highlighting the power of collaboration in improving AF care. Several of our partners, including LJMU, UoL, SHS and RUMC, joined the celebrations by wearing something red and posting on social media.

MEET OUR YOUNG RESEARCHERS

Postdoctoral researcher at TARGET, applying my machine learning expertise from astrophysics to revolutionise stroke care in Atrial Fibrillation patients

Dr Dharmesh Mistry

Hi all,
as a postdoctoral researcher at TARGET, I am developing the data-driven aspect of the virtual twin AI models using patient-specific data (e.g., risk factors, comorbidities, imaging, and biomarkers). When combined with mechanistic models of the heart, brain, and neuromusculoskeletal system, these virtual patient representations will play a pivotal role in the goals of TARGET.

One of the most fascinating aspects of my work is navigating the complexity of multimodal (tabular, time-series, and imaging) healthcare datasets. Although challenging, working with this data provides deep insights into patient health and allows me to explore the intersection of healthcare and AI. I'm particularly excited about applying generative AI to these diverse data types. It not only allows me to work with cutting-edge AI models but also to contribute to advancing the field by addressing the unique challenges of applying these techniques in healthcare.

What I find most rewarding is the collaborative nature of this project. Working alongside experts in cardiology, neurology, biomedical engineering, and AI from institutions across Europe has been incredibly inspiring. Together, we have the potential to make a meaningful difference in patients' lives, which is a driving force behind my work and the project as a whole.

Dr. Adam T. Knowles, Postdoctoral Research Associate at the Data Science Research Centre, Liverpool John Moores University, joins TARGET to support and develop risk prediction modelling of AF and AFRS using AI and ML methodologies.

Dr Adam T. Knowles

Hi all,

I'm Adam Knowles, a Postdoctoral Research Associate at the Data Science Research Centre within Liverpool John Moores University and an

affiliate member of the Liverpool Centre for Cardiovascular Science. I joined TARGET in July 2024, where my work mainly focusses on WP5 and related areas. My primary role centres on applying and advancing ML and AI techniques to support the development of digital twin models, decision-support tools and dynamic, personalised risk prediction models for AF and AF-related stroke.

I am thrilled to be part of this large-scale medical research project, which brings together a diverse collaboration between academia and industry, offering me an exciting opportunity to work in an interesting, impactful and rapidly advancing field. Although my background is in astrophysics, where I completed my Ph.D. modelling stellar populations and galactic chemical evolution, I have always been drawn to research with tangible, real-world benefits.

After postdoctoral roles in Barcelona and Tenerife, I returned to the UK as an Impact Officer at LJMU, helping academics across the university plan for, manage and demonstrate the impact of their research. This role further fuelled my passion for research that drives real-world change, making TARGET's aims to revolutionise personalised healthcare using the latest developments of AI and ML a natural next career step for me.

I'm looking forward to working within the collaboration and contributing to the project's progress and impact over the coming years.

TARGET

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Partners

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